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Determining the Training Needs and Qualification Levels of Counsellor Candidates regarding “Therapeutic Skills” in the Process of Individual Counseling Training

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Abstract

This study is aimed at determining the training needs and qualification levels of counseling candidates concerning invitation to speak, reflecting feelings, minimal encouragement, reflection of content, personalization, self-addition, self-disclosure, summarization and confrontation skills during the psychological counseling process. In the present study, summative content analysis was used. 20 students (12 female, 8 male) who took Individual Counseling Course in the spring term of 2019- 2020 academic year constitute the study group. “Counselor Qualifications Evaluation Form” developed by Eryılmaz and Mutlu- Süral was employed to identify the qualifications regarding the skills. Supervision was observed to be sufficient in terms of developing the qualifications of minimal encouragement, reflection of content, reflecting feelings (except from counselor’s prolonged speech), summarization and self- disclosure. On the contrary, it was seen that supervision was not sufficient in developing other qualifications as personalization, initiation to speak and self- addition and it was found that candidates needed training regarding confrontation skills.

Keywords: Therapeutic Skills, Individual Counseling, Qualification Level

1. Introduction

It has been acknowledged that psychological counseling education in Turkey is mainly carried out at undergraduate level as well as master’s and doctoral programs. In this regard, it can be said that Individual Counseling is a course for students studying at undergraduate level in the field of psychological counseling education through which they, for the first time, are able to put their psychological counseling skills and theoretical knowledge gained during their education into practice for clients to provide psychological assistance. Therefore, it has been thought that the training carried out within the scope of this course plays a pivotal role as the students gain the opportunity to acquire a real psychological counseling experience and take steps towards occupational self- concept of psychological counseling (Meydan, 2014).

On a national scale, it has been stated that, according to some researchers, it is not known how and what quality this training is provided to counseling candidates within the scope of Individual Counseling course (Aladağ and Kemer, 2016; Siviş, Çetinkaya and Karanmak, 2012). Büyükgöze and Kavas (2011) revealed the different practices regarding psychological counseling process among universities. In addition, Atik (2012) states that there is no standard set for the psychological counseling practices in Turkey and adds that this training do not become adequately widespread. Consequently, it has been seen that there are certain problems related to this field and prospective expectations of improvement.

It is possible to put forward that the problems within the context of the topics touched upon in the field of Individual Counseling are rooted in the problems related to the standards in our country as well as the ones arising from the nature of the profession. The difficulties faced by counselor candidates at the earlier levels of education are regarded as the necessity of their training. These difficulties may be fulfilling internship requirements, seeing a large number of clients, performing reading activities and doing homework (Howard et al., 2006). Furthermore, another challenge that counselor candidates encounter is that they are required to realize the old ways of psychological assistance- such as advising and seeking immediate solutions- are no longer functional and to try to acquire new skills as active listening and reflecting feelings (Ronnestad and Skovholt, 2003). Besides, the counselor candidates need to develop prepared and cautious attitudes in order to perform psychological counseling services properly. Psychological counsellor candidates should avoid taking unnecessary risks when trying to help their clients in a best way and making decisions on their own in relation to the client. The counselor candidates should be relaxed with the counseling process and make the client feel that the counseling process is under his/her control. Since they do not completely know how and what to do due to lack of knowledge, skills and experience in general, high anxiety, self- criticism and self- doubt and confrontation may be considered as the difficulties faced by earlier periods of the training (Woodside et al., 2007). In order to overcome these difficulties, the supervisors, instructors and lecturers are said to be the most effective individuals in psychological counseling education, as of the very first practices, for counselor candidates (Tanhan, 2018). It has been emphasized that as these critical difficulties experienced by counselor candidates are regarded as developmentally natural in the profession, those who are involved in psychological counseling education are able to overcome those challenges through the preventive approaches of supervisors or lecturers prior to the practices (Borders, 2016; Tarhan, 2018).

One of the fundamental prerequisites of effective psychological counseling assistance is that the person who provides psychological help is also an effective counselor (Hackney and Cormier 2005; Meydan, 2014). On the other hand, being an effective psychological counsellor may be possible by having certain theoretical knowledge and skills as well as supporting those knowledge and skills with psychological counseling practices (Gibson and Mitchell 2008; Meydan, 2014). As a result, it can be uttered that counselor candidates can only acquire such a fund of knowledge by completing an adequate and effective education.

Meydan (2014) highlights that psychological counseling skills consist of both verbal and non-verbal skills, and that their most basic function is to enable counselors to communicate with their clients. Accordingly, professionals who provide psychological assistance are required to have gained a number of acquisitions in order to be successful in the process of psychological help.

Therapy is the process of establishing a relationship and gaining trust between the counselor and the client. To facilitate this relationship, counselors need highly advanced therapeutic skills. Therapeutic skills are verbal and non- verbal ways to communicate with clients with the aim of creating an emotional environment in which a therapeutic bond (agreement) can be formed, maintained and safely terminated. This relationship is crucial to help clients discover how their life experiences affect their ways of being, and, if they want, to find new meanings and ways to relate to themselves, others and life (Ingram and Robson, 2018). As stated by Eryılmaz and Mutlu- Süral (2014), therapeutic skills include invitation to speak, reflecting feelings, minimal encouragement, reflection of content, personalization, self- addition, self-disclosure, summarization, confrontation and structuring.

One of the main assumptions of curriculum development is that a robust curriculum should be based on students' needs analysis. The processes used to gather information regarding students' needs are known as needs analysis (Richards, 2001). Need recognition is a series of systematic processes determined for the purpose of identifying

needs, making decisions and setting principles about the curriculum or dividing corporate development and resources (Witkin and Altschuld, 1995). However, needs assessment is used to address the majority of areas of educational programming and student development (such as academic, emotional, social, professional, aesthetical, physical and moral) at local, state, regional and national levels. Needs assessment is a process that can be utilized for a number of different purposes, such as helping planning, identifying and diagnosing problems, and helping assess the merit and value of another program or effort (Stufflebeam et al., 1985). Needs refer to the difference between what the current situation is and what it should be (Sönmez et al., 2019). The difference between expected competencies and performance of the counselor candidates may give an idea about their educational needs while designing a curriculum concerning individual counseling skills of counselor candidates. The curriculum to be developed based on this knowledge may facilitate acquiring expected competencies and guide the development of individual counseling education curricula.

The current study is designed to determine the training needs and qualification levels of counselor candidates concerning 'therapeutic skills' in the process of individual counseling. This study aims to examine candidates' training needs and qualification levels towards invitation to speak, reflecting feelings, minimal encouragement, reflection of content, personalization, self-addition, self-disclosure, summarization and confrontation skills. Through this study, it was attempted to determine the frequency and competency levels of the therapeutic skills, constituting psychological counseling process, exhibited by counseling candidates over time. In addition, their training needs regarding individual counseling competencies were tried to be revealed. Therefore, it is thought that the training needs and qualification levels in the field revealed in the present study may contribute to the educational quality in psychological counseling field.

2. Method

Qualitative data analysis is a process in which researcher organizes the data, divides it into units, synthesizes, reveals patterns, explores significant variables and decides what information to include in his/ her report (Bogdan and Biklen, 1992; Walcott, 1994). Since the main purpose of this study is to determine what supervisory skills shown by candidates are, at what level they are able to perform these skills and what are their needs in the 'Individual Counseling' course, the qualitative approach was adopted in the current study.

In the study, the recordings of 8 sessions carried out by counseling candidates who participated in the study were obtained. Through these records, the therapeutic skills of counseling candidates were investigated based on "Counselor Qualifications Evaluation Form" and research data were collected by marking 'Yes' if the candidate showed a behaviour concerning the related skill and 'No' if s/he did not. If the candidate exhibited a behaviour related to one of the therapeutic skills in a session, it was considered sufficient for the relevant session; however, it was not examined how many times s/he repeated this skill in the same session. It was investigated that the level of use of therapeutic skills, in other words, whether the candidates are able to use the skills at expected quality in the relevant session. For this reason, content analysis, which is one of the qualitative research methods, was included in the study. As content analysis, summative content analysis was used. In a study that employed summative content analysis, the first step is to identify and measure specific words or content in the text in order to comprehend the textual use of the words or content. This quantification is not an attempt to grasp meaning; rather, to explore usage. Beyond the count of words or appropriate sentences is the interpretation of the content. In this regard, the main focus is on exploring the meanings underlying the words or content (Hsieh and Shanon, 2005). Content analysis, which is one of the qualitative research methods, was used in this study, the main purpose of whose is to determine the training needs and qualification levels of counselor candidates concerning 'therapeutic skills' in the process of individual counseling. Content analysis is mainly based on the analysis of written and visual data. In the content analysis, categories related to the research subject are generated and then, words and sentences are assigned to these categories in accordance with the data obtained from the candidates examined and, finally, counting are performed (Silverman, 2001).

2.1. Population and Sample of the Study

20 students (12 female, 8 male) who took Individual Counseling Course in the spring term of 2019- 2020 academic year constitute the study group.

2.2. Data Collection Instruments

Within the scope of Individual Counseling Course, candidates were requested to perform eight sessions and audio recording were asked for each of the sessions. The candidates were, then, asked to decode the recordings. Based on approximately 120 hours of recordings, candidates' training needs and qualification levels were investigated according to the identified categories. Since these qualifications require to be examined in terms of certain criteria and categories, "Counselor Qualifications Evaluation Form" developed for use in "Developmental Comprehensive Supervision Model" developed by Eryilmaz and Mutlu- Süral (2014) was employed. The form includes four main sections and sub- sections as *structuring* (duration, process, objective), *therapeutic conditions* (concreteness, transparency, empathy, here and now, respect), *therapeutic skills* (invitation to speak, reflecting feelings, minimal encouragement, reflection of content, personalization, self- addition, self- disclosure, summarization and confrontation skills) and *managing therapeutic process* (managing the client, managing self and managing the counseling process). As the current study centred upon therapeutics skills, only the skills under this title were examined. If the candidate exhibited the behaviour included in the form, 'Yes' option was marked and it s/he did not, 'No' option was marked. For instance, if the candidate asked a question related to invitation to speak skill, then 'Yes' option was marked and the question or statement used by her/ him was noted under the 'invitation to speak' category. Following, the suitability of the question or statement in terms of the purpose of use was evaluated and the counsellor candidates' training needs and qualification levels in terms of the related skill were decided.

With the aim of ensuring the confidentiality of the participants, codes ranging from C1 to C-20 were used instead of their names. The current study was actually based on recordings of the sessions. However, from time to time, either group interviews or client- supervisor interviews were conducted to have a better understanding on the behaviours of counselor candidates.

3. Findings

This section covers the findings regarding the skills of invitation to speak, reflecting feelings, minimal encouragement, reflection of content, personalization, self- addition, self- disclosure, summarization and confrontation.

3.1. Findings regarding Minimal Encouragement Skill

Minimal encouragement is the responses by counselors to encourage their clients to explain more about themselves and their problems. According to the transcription of the recordings carried out in 8 sessions of 20 counselor candidates, it was determined that the candidates fulfilled this skill at expected qualification at the end of the supervision performed after the sessions. It was revealed that, during counseling process, candidates were able to encourage the clients to speak by asking questions consisting of "humm," "yes" or one word or by repeating the keywords that represent the main idea in the client's statements. In one of the interviews conducted by C7, s/he was revealed to use this skill as follows:

Client: *I said I was going to be a teacher. But I went there so ignorant.*

C-7: *I see.*

Client: *My teacher said never mind. My father said to my teacher s/he knew the best. He told me he knew the best. I mean, I went there without knowing anything.*

C-7: *So, you didn't know anything about it?*

Client: *Exactly. Without knowing anything, I just whaled into it.*

As seen in this sample, the counselor candidate appropriately uses minimal encouragement skill and carries forward the counseling process and generates the suitable environment for the client to encourage her/ him to speak more about herself/ himself.

It was found that the common mistakes made by candidates regarding “minimal encouragement” skill were that they used the phrases such as ‘I see, Hi Hi!, Yes’ and ‘Alright’ very often and did not use expressions or other therapeutic skills that would contribute to the process and help themselves understand the client and enable the client to express her/ his feelings and thoughts. Nevertheless, it was determined that as the sessions continued, the number of mistakes were observed to decrease; especially after the sixth session, there were no unnecessary uses encountered.

3.2. Findings regarding Reflection of Content Skill

The reflection of content is to clarify the client’s statements in terms of content, and to reconvey his/ her statements by summarizing them in different words without affecting the content. The main purpose of this skill is to check whether the client’s thoughts are correctly understood by the counselor, to make the client’s thoughts more explicitly expresses and to ensure the client’s thoughts to be understood. According to the content analysis, it was seen that this skill is the one that the candidates were the most competent. It was determined that nearly none of 20 candidates used it incorrectly. A sample of correct use is as follows:

Client: *One of the first things is to feel incomplete about certain things like this. Then comes the idea that I can’t do anything on the test. And then there is forgetfulness during the exam, which is probably related to anxiety. This affects stress level a lot. And the attitudes of the teachers in the classroom may be related to the increasing level of stress.*

C-12: *You think you’re going to fail the test you feel incomplete, and the teachers’ behaviours increases your anxiety level.*

Client: *Yes, that’s exactly what it is. In fact, I could deal with them all if I could tell them apart.*

As this sample shows, the counselor candidate correctly used reflection of content skill. The fact that the client says ‘Yes, that’s exactly what it is’ is an indication that the candidate has used the reflection of content skill correctly. Similarly, other candidates were found to effectively use this skill. On the contrary, although it was not common, when the recordings were examined, the mistake identified was that the candidates asked close- ended questions such as “Do they have the same feelings as you?” (C- 10), “Are you angry with your flatmates?” (C- 6) and “Are you thinking of leaving the department you’re studying?” (C- 17). These mistakes, in particular, were observed during the very first sessions; however, it was determined that this skill was fully fulfilled after the supervision. *It may be concluded that the candidates’ performances on the reflection of content skill are an indication that there is no training needed towards this skill.*

3. Findings regarding Personalization Skill

Personalization is of importance in the counseling process in order for client to clarify the purpose of his/ her having psychological counseling by discovering herself/ himself and to ensure that the client owns the existing problem to properly resolve the problem. When this skill is not used, the purpose may be prevented from clarifying and, therefore, the solution may not be developed. The analyses revealed that the personalization skill was not frequently used. It was found that counselor candidates used reflection of content skill in the sessions that stated that ‘we used.’

Client: *My roommate. She’s the problem. She’s an untidy, sloppy and messy person who doesn’t put the things in their place. She doesn’t hang her clothes neatly in her closet, put her books in her bookcase and, then, she asks us. I’m overwhelmed. I can’t stand that anymore.*

C-15: *This mess, Ash’s mess, bothers you.*

Client: *Exactly.*

C-15: *To be organized is important for you. You can’t stand untidiness. It makes you angry to have an untidy space in the same house even if you are staying in separate rooms.*

It was determined that C-15 used the personalization skill correctly during the counseling process, allowing a clear understanding of the problem by the client. C-15 was observed to attempt to help the client understand the real problem by using reflection of content skills.

At the end of supervision process, it was seen that the counselor candidates were not able to administer the personalization skill at expected level of competence. A sample of this was given below:

Client: *When I graduate, I want to start my master's degree right away, but I don't have a job. I had better get a job first. Then, I'm thinking of applying for a master's degree. But this time, there is military service. If I work, I have to go to the army, so I give up the idea of having master's degree. If I did a master's degree, military service would be deferred as I was a student, but this time it would be difficult for me to have a career. I'm so confused.*

C-20: *You think a master's degree will help defer military service, but it will prevent you from getting a job?*

In the sample above, the candidate attempted to use personalization skill. However, s/ he exhibited a behaviour that was not suitable for personalization skill by converting the client's statements into a question. Instead, it would be right to use such a statement as "You can't decide what to do because you think that doing a master's degree will help defer military service but will also hinder you to get a job" for personalization skill. As a result, it may be concluded that candidates need training towards personalization skill.

4. Findings regarding Reflecting Feelings Skill

Reflecting feelings skill is related to clarifying the client's feelings. This skill is used to clarify the client's feelings and to check whether the counselor perceives his/ her feelings correctly. Reflecting feelings skill is the determination and transmission of the feelings about the problems of the clients that they have difficulty in identifying. It is important to determine the client's feelings related to his/ her problem properly in order to have a positive impact on the communication between the counselor and the client. The counselor candidates were found to be able to use this skill by accurately determining what the clients felt during the counseling process. The conversation below may be given as a sample:

Client: *I'm home and crying. I'm already very affected from this.*

C-7: *Alright, you got on the board in class. Did you get any feedback from your classmates in this process, any reaction to you, etc?*

Client: *They laughed.*

C-7: *And that made you sadder.*

Although reflection feelings skill was generally used correctly, certain counselor candidates were not able to use this skill required by the psychological process correctly as in C-15.

Client: *I was in the certification program as usual at the weekend. I'm in the same place seven days a week. If you can't reach me you know that I'm at school. And in class, as a matter of fact, this week was good and so were the subjects. There was nothing to me off. On the contrary, good things happened. For example, the subjects were really nice when we discussed nice things as love poems.*

C-15: *It's been a very emotional week for you.*

In the sample above, the fact that the candidate summarized the client's experiences in a general sense without fully reflecting his/ her experiences prevents him/ her from noticing the intensity of his/ her feelings. In this respect, the candidate was not able to use the reflecting feelings skill correctly and appropriately. It was determined that candidates had difficulty in determining reflecting feelings, particularly in long speeches of the client.

5. Findings regarding Summarization Skill

The summarization skill is an important skill that facilitates two-way communication to occur, helps the clients to ease and contributes to the solution of the problem gradually in the psychological counseling process. According to Voltan-

Acar (2020), this skill refers to summarizing a certain part or whole of the consultation process by using it in company with feelings or content reflection. It was determined that the candidates were able to use summarization skill correctly.

C-5: ...*We talked about identity confusion last week. You said you were confusing your roles and when I first asked when this happened, it actually started this year. Because I was a student for 20 years. I haven't adapted since I started business life. I'm going to İzmir, I'm still my mother's daughter and still young but I'm coming here. You said you had to be mature and it was tiring to be caught in the way of it... In fact, it's affecting your life. You mentioned it was a little negative. Last week, you went to İzmir and you said that it was good for you.*

C-9: *Now, to sum up, you think that you should never make mistakes, because your mother especially wants you to do. You're afraid of making mistakes, but you're making the mistakes that you don't do by losing control as you are trying not to make mistakes. And it makes you extremely uncomfortable.*

Summarization also refers to the confirmation from the points of view of both parties that the process continues in a correct way. It contributes to the process to continue properly and to achieve the desired outcomes. It was observed that the candidates were able to use this skill effectively during 8- session- counseling process.

6. Findings regarding Invitation to Speak Skill

The purpose of invitation to speak skill is to be able to understand the feelings, thoughts and experiences of the clients directly or indirectly related to the problem. It is a skill that the counselor requires to use effectively in order for the client to express herself/ himself better. According to the examination of recordings, the counselor candidates used this skill through open- ended questions.

Client: *Anger is reflected in daily life. When I get up this morning, it raises questions about whether I should go to the class or not. I'm more withdrawn when I talk to people. It affects my circle of friends. Maybe I know someone less that I can know better. Our relationship is not so close although we can have a close relationship. We can say that it affects my home, friends, my classes and everything in my daily life.*

C-20: *Anxiety, anger, do you think they affect your daily life and relations with other people?*

Client: *Yes.*

C-20: *So, this anxiety affects your relations physically. Can you explain a little bit how these will affect you in the future?*

As seen in the example above, the candidate attempted to provide a clear understanding of what is the main situation affecting the quality of life of the client. Moreover, the candidate also attempted to demonstrate the importance of the situation for the client by asking open- ended questions.

It was shown that the counselor candidates were able to use invitation to speak skill successfully. However, in certain sessions, it was observed that this skill was not used when it was required to be used.

Client: *For example, I had a friend from secondary school. We were very close to each other those times. It was a boy. He wasn't very good with the girls. We were just friends and already talking. Then, at the high school, last summer, or maybe not last summer, but the summer before because we were at the high school. He texted me, and we started talking. I speak as if I am talking with an ordinary friend because he's just my friend. I don't see him in a different way. But he said that he loved me, sometimes he told me such nice words, compliments that I've never heard before. And if a man is over-complimenting to you, you shouldn't trust him. I didn't trust, either. After that, we talked for about a month or two. Even though I said I didn't trust him, I inevitably got used to those words and compliments, and, after a while, I start to feel normal. You're starting to feel confident even if you don't say it orally. Then, he suddenly stopped talking and I found out that he was talking to another girl. I felt so bad. I mean, you don't normally love him, so why does a person cry. I felt myself cheated. It was so bad. It's been two years since then and I haven't talked to anyone. I mean as a boyfriend.*

C-13: *Okay, I see.*

In this example, the fact that the candidate says “Okay, I see” may not contribute to the client to see the problem, to discover herself. In addition, it may also affect the counseling process adversely. Instead, it would be appropriate for the candidate to deepen and make the problem more pronounced by asking open- ended questions such as “*How has your situation with just one person affected your sense of trust in other people?*”

While asking open- ended questions to fulfill the invitation to speak skill, it was determined that the counselor candidate asked questions in order to satisfy his/ her own curiosity in two sessions. The situation in one of the sessions is presented below:

Client: *I have siblings in my family who study like me but I couldn't get used to the school. Some nights, I wake up crying in the dorm. My friends are always there for me, I thank them. There are friends who smoke, sometimes they smoke in front of the window in the room. That smell when the match burns reminds me of my father, I feel like crying and running away, going home. I don't want to be there.*

C-13: *How many brothers or sisters are you?*

Client: *Two brothers, three sisters. There's a lot of us.*

C-13: *How do your friends help you, what do they do?*

In invitation to speak skill, counselor candidates were observed to use such a phrase as “I see” often. However, in certain sessions, when this phrase is used repeatedly, it does not contribute to the counseling process.

7. Findings regarding Self- Addition Skill

In the psychological counseling process, the counselor's participation in the positive or negative feelings of the client and in his/ her opinion and the client's ability to show his/ her own reaction is called as self- addition. The key point in using this skill is to clarify the problem of the client, to approve his/ her correct behaviours towards the solution of the problem and to encourage the client to act. In this respect, it is one of the important skills of the psychological counseling process.

In the 160 sessions examined, it was determined that self- addition skill was used correctly. One of the examples where this skill was used correctly is as follows:

Client: *I'm yelling at him. I'm calling him. I'm hitting him when it's time. If he understood at once, it's best to solve by talking to him.*

C-17: *Yes, it's best to talk it out. Any other approach might make him more vicious. And now that he's a teenager, he can do the things he wouldn't do.*

As seen in this example, the candidate agrees that the solution of the client is the right method. The candidate explains what the client may face if this method is used.

In the recordings investigated, it was determined that self- addition skill appeared in the form of reflection of feelings and content and that the candidates were not able to use this skill sufficiently.

Client: *Studying in Uşak... there's nothing here, there's nothing to do.*

C-16: *You don't feel free!*

Client: *The teacher and I didn't hit it off. I'll be so relieved if I know what to do. If another teacher gives the same class, I'll take it. I'll even take the class next year again. There's one lecturer in the department so it doesn't matter! I don't know how to fix my relationship with my teacher or whether I should do this or not.*

C-10: *You're doubtful about what to do, you're having conflicting feelings. I had a similar problem I was at the university.*

In the supervision process with the counselor candidates, it was determined that the candidates did not fully understand the self- addition skill. *As a result of the supervision, this skill was used by nine candidates at the desired quality in the following sessions; however, the remaining candidates were not able to use this skill sufficiently.*

8. Findings regarding Self- Disclosure Skill

Self- disclosure skill refers to the counselor's talking about his/ her own life and feelings related to the client's problem. In other words, the counselor shares his/ her own feelings and thoughts about the client's problem with the client. This skill is of importance in that it helps the client understand and solve the problem. When the recordings obtained from the sessions were examined, it was found that the counselor candidates were able to use this skill properly and appropriately.

Client: Talking before a crowd makes me so nervous, I feel sweat coming out of the middle of my back. I don't know why this is happening. Actually, I'm prepared for the subject I'm talking about, but when I'm in front of people, I'm cut off. I feel like I'm going to say something that's irrelevant. I'm stuck.

C-8: Actually, I had a similar experience in high school. And I was thinking "I'd rather do a heavy work, I mean physically, than talk in front of a crowd."

As in the example above, the candidate continues the psychological assistance process with an example from his/ her own life to make the client feel better. Although not often, it was determined that the candidates disclose themselves in a way that does not contribute to the counseling process.

Client: You know, the dorm is crowded. If you tried to work in the room, you wouldn't be able to work. There's a study room, and people would talk while studying there. You can't work.

C-11: Noise bothers you, I can't work in a noisy environment, either.

Client: No, the noise doesn't bother me too much, but the crowd distracts me. When everyone's dealing with other things, it's just the curiosity about what's s/he doing, what other people are doing.

The candidate discloses himself/ herself without completely understanding the problem. It might have been more effective if s/he had used self- disclosure skill after understanding the problem through invitation to speak skill.

9. Findings regarding Confrontation Skill

Confrontation is when the counselor fulfills the empathy condition and reveals the inconsistencies s/ he observes. It is, in other words, a skill used to express the contradictions of the client regarding the problem in the counseling process (Eryılmaz and Mutlu-Süral, 2014). Using this skill, the counselor attempts to contribute to the solution of the problem by enabling the clients to be aware of their feelings, thoughts and behaviours by focusing on the discrepancies among them. When the recordings were examined, it was found that candidates did not use this skill.

10. Result and Discussion

This study is aimed at determining the training needs and qualification levels of counseling candidates concerning invitation to speak, reflecting feelings, minimal encouragement, reflection of content, personalization, self-addition, self- disclosure, summarization and confrontation skills during the psychological counseling process. It was determined in the current study that the counselor candidates were not able to use the skills of personalization, self- addition, self-disclosure, summarization and confrontation at desired levels. The supervision activities carried out were not sufficient for the candidates to fully acquire these skills.

Although not often, candidates were observed to affect counseling process adversely by asking unnecessary questions in terms of invitation to speak skill among therapeutic skills. Furthermore, by over-using such patterns as "yes, I see," they caused them to lose their effectiveness and meaning. Ivey et al. (2006) describe the question as an open invitation. However, questions are often perceived as intrusive by clients, in spite of they are seemingly harmless (Cormier, 2016).

Through the supervision conducted in the current study, it was attempted to prevent the candidate from asking unnecessary questions. Nevertheless, the candidates continue making this mistake due to their lack of experience. Candidates need to be shown what open-ended and close-ended questions are and where they should use them.

Carkhuff (2008) stated that personalization skill is the most challenging interpersonal skill to learn and apply. It can be said that it may not be easy for the counselor candidates to gain this skill with their applications consisting of eight sessions in the study. For a high-level personalization skill, a counselor candidate requires to understand the client's problems, objectives, feelings and to catch the deficits; however, for a low-level personalization skill, s/he requires to accurately report the meaning of what the client says (Bernard & Goodyear: 2019). In this regard, it may be concluded that the counselor candidates need more practice and supervision for a high-level personalization skill. It may be asserted that personalization skill may not easily enhance through the applications required by Individual Counseling course since students have to pay attention to a number of features in the counseling process and to use various skills at the same time. It may be argued that it may be possible to develop the skills that are intended to be acquired in the applications performed with not fully acquired skills. In order for the counselor candidates to be effective in the counseling process, personalization skill and other skills are required to be acquired in advance with a certain qualification before applying.

It is important to use therapeutic skills in the counseling process; however, the fact that counselor candidates are not adequately qualified for these skills affects the use of these skills. In a study conducted by Şahin et al. (2019), counselor candidates highlighted the importance of using these skills. Nonetheless, the frequency of use of these skills varies. The candidates were observed to use reflection of content skill the least.

As a result of this study, it was determined that the frequency of use of therapeutic skills was different. Therefore, the findings of the current study have yielded different results from those of the study carried out by Şahin et al. In the study, the candidates were observed not to use confrontation skill. It is not appropriate to use confrontation skill in the first session; this skill is used in the later sessions of the counseling process when the client-counselor trust is provided (Cormier, 2016). According to Developmental Assistance Model, it is a skill that should be used by the counselor when the benefit of client is believed towards the end of the phase of client's self-understanding (Eryılmaz and Mutlu-Süral: 2014). In this respect, the candidates should bring the client to the level of confrontation by using certain skills as structuring, therapeutic conditions and managing therapeutic process. In case there is lack in previous skills, this may have negative effects on the counseling process (Bek and Gülveren, 2021).

In the present study, where counselor candidates were examined in terms of therapeutic skills, it may be concluded that they need training concerning personalization and confrontation skills. The qualification level of the candidates may be enhanced by generating a curriculum for the development of these skills. During these trainings, it is possible to allow the candidates make practice and, based on their experiences, the skill may be acquired by using such different methods as micro- teaching where they are able to gain skills by evaluating themselves.

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